

Morphogenetic Features, Soil Properties and Nature of Parent Materials in Relation to Development of Some Nun River Plain Soils in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Alluvial soils form from processes of erosion and sedimentation, exhibiting characteristics reflecting composition and properties of the material transported, varying spatially and temporally, reflecting heterogeneity of the floodplain system. Texture, organic carbon distribution and clay mineralogy are commonly used features/indicators of the homogeneity or otherwise of parent materials. Since the floodplain soils of Nun River, Southern Nigeria lack information, nine soil profiles from different landforms were examined for their morphogenetic features, physico-chemical and mineralogical characteristics and heterogeneity of parent materials in relation to soil development. Surface soils had darker hues (10YR) becoming redder (7.5 YR) with depth, displaying redoximorphic

features, sometimes reaching A-horizon with subsurface graying. Heterogeneity in soil characteristics was obvious, parent materials and degree of hydromorphism moulding morphogenesis and gleization, a major contemporary pedogenetic process. Silt loam dominated texture followed by silty clayloam and loam. Soils were moderately acid to slightly acid [pH-(H₂O), 5.42-6.49], low to high organic matter (0.19-9.05%) and total N (0.01-0.45%), low to moderate available P (0.6-22 mg/kg), low to moderate (0.09-1.51cmol/kg) exchangeable K while Ca²⁺ dominated the exchange sites. Quartz dominated mineral phases followed by microcline, albite, muscovite as well as kaolinite while ferromagnesian minerals concentration was low. Wetness, flooding, and soil chemical and physical fertility are constraints to increased and sustainable crop production. Therefore, organic matter application should be encouraged while more detailed mineralogical studies is recommended to serve a useful guide in the management of the soils for agricultural intensification and food security.

Keywords: *Morphogenetic features, floodplain soils, mineralogical characteristics, parent materials.*

Introduction

Alluvial landforms are major agricultural baskets in several regions (Umeugochukwu et al., 2019) and differences in soil characteristics associated with landscape position are usually attributed to differences in the runoff, erosion and deposition

processes which ultimately affect soil genesis (Canton et al., 2003). Alluvial soils which result from processes of erosion and deposition, exhibit various characteristics which reflect the composition and properties of the material transported (Weber & Gobat, 2006). The

processes of sedimentation and erosion vary spatially and temporally, contributing to the heterogeneity of the whole floodplain system.

Texture, organic carbon distribution and clay mineralogy are features commonly used as indicators of the homogeneity or otherwise of the parent materials of alluvial origin (Dickson et al., 2022).

Irregularity in the distribution of sand, silt and clay in soil profiles has been associated with sediments types having different textures deposited yearly according to their sources (Azagaku and Idoga, 2012). Variability in the trend of texture of soils has been attributed to differences in parent material and topography (Abua, 2012). Also, the very fine sand and fine sand proportions are used to indicate lithologic discontinuities. Essoka and Esu (2000), reported that silt/clay ratio of less than unity indicated low values and could mean that the soils are pedo-genetically ferralitic. For the Lower Niger River floodplain soils, Dickson et al. (2022) ascribed textural diversity between different SMUs to differences in sources of the water-borne sediments and the flow rate of the floodwater at the time of deposition of the parent materials while differences in organic carbon distribution patterns indicated stratification and heterogeneity of parent materials.

Khan et al (2012) associated reduction in pH of flooded soils to ferrolysis which is acidification of topsoil caused by continual displacement of bases by ferrous ion during the reduction phase associated with annual flooding. Soil Survey Staff (2014) associated irregular decrease in organic matter content with depth as consistent with the properties of fluvents while Tisdale et al. (2008) attributed low exchangeable bases in soils to acidifying properties of organic matter, high aluminium concentration and leaching loss of exchangeable bases.

Though the Nun River floodplain soils of Bayelsa state are believed to have high agricultural potentials, current information and knowledge on the dominant soil forming processes, soil characteristics including mineralogical composition, and the

homogeneity of parent materials or otherwise are inadequate and/or obsolete. Even the characterization and classification of alluvial soils of the Nun River floodplains did not provide necessary information on the morphogenetic features, mineralogical status and/or nature of parent materials in relation to their development which could be resourceful indicators for proper policy formulation by government. With present drive of the Bayelsa State government towards self-sufficiency in rice production, the efficient management of the soils for increase and sustainable rice and other food crop production cannot be over emphasized and this cannot be achieved with the present level of information and knowledge on the soils. The aim of this study, therefore, is to examine the morphogenetic features, physico-chemical, mineralogical properties and nature of the parent materials of soils of Odi, Koroama and Niger Delta University earmarked by the Bayelsa State government for agricultural intensification and rice production.

Description of the Study Areas

The study locations are captured in Dickson et al. (2021) which lie between latitude $05^{\circ} 22' 03.9''$ N and $04^{\circ} 59' 08.9''$ N and longitude $006^{\circ} 30' 21.1''$ E and $006^{\circ} 06' 54.1''$ E all in Bayelsa State in the Niger Delta region, Southern Nigeria. Niger River flows southward and breaks up into two—the Forcados and Nun Rivers in Bayelsa State; the Nun River, runs north and south down the middle of the Bayelsa State, which remains the most direct tributary of the Niger. The Odi community lie by the Nun River on the western bank, Koroama community, by Taylor Creek that receives waters from the Nun River and Niger Delta University (Amassoma) by the Nun River down south towards the Atlantic Ocean (Fig. 1) were chosen for the study due to the proposed agricultural intensification. The annual rainfall is 2000-4500mm, spread over 8 to 10 months of the year and bimodal, peaking at June and September. The relative humidity averages 80% all over the state and temperature is fairly constant with a maximum of 30°C . The natural vegetation is tropical rainforest. Food is cultivated on the levee crest, levee slope, backslope and on recent alluvial soils on

channels of present active rivers. The levee crest soils are no longer flooded while most flood plain soils are flooded yearly by the Niger River floods according to Anderson (1966) but most levee crest soils are being flooded in recent years due to climate change.

Soil Sampling and Analyses

Details of soil survey on the Odi, Koroama and Niger Delta University Wilberforce Island are also captured by Dickson et al. (2021). As stated in that report, soil mapping units (SMUs) designations were ODI1, ODI 2 and ODI3 for Odi, KRM1, KRM2, and KRM3 for Koroama soils and NDU1, NDU2 and NDU3 for Niger

Delta University Teaching and Research farm, Details of the soil mapping units and the land area are presented in table 1. Soil sampling procedures followed the methods as prescribed by the USDA Soil Taxonomy and the World Resource Base. Soil samples collected were air-dried, crushed and sieved to pass through a 2 mm mesh and analyzed in the Green River Project laboratory of the Nigerian Agip Oil Company and Zadell laboratory, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Standard laboratory procedures were used to determine the physical and chemical properties of the soil samples as reported in Dickson et al (2021) and Dickson et al. (2022).

Figure 1. Map of Bayelsa State, Nigeria Showing Sampling Locations

Table 1. Soil Mapping Unit, Profile Pit Location and Land Area

Study Location	Soil Mapping Unit	Geo-reference of Profile Pit	No. of Profile Pit	Land Area (Hectares)	Land Area (%)
Odi	ODI1	N 05° 11' 17.4" E 006° 18' 04.6"	1	142.485670	11.7
	ODI2	N 05° 11' 17.1", E006° 17' 52.3"	1	65.061343	5.3

	ODI3	N 05° 11' 38.7"" E 006° 17' 47.0"	1	138.649761	11.4
Koroama	KRM1	N 05° 02' 59.9", E 006° 17' 28.8"	1	13.182619	1.1
	KRM2	N 05° 02' 59.2", E 006° 17' 26.9"	1	10.647992	0.9
	KRM3	N 05° 02' 58.1", E 006° 17' 14.0"	1	21.428567	1.8
Niger Delta University	NDU1	N 04° 58' 49.1" E 006° 06' 23.7"	1	24.048062	2.0
	NDU2	N 04° 58' 49.9", E 006° 06' 17.5"	1	7.533081	0.6
	NDU3	N 04° 58' 50.5", E 006° 06' 15.7"	1	60.527688	5.0

Results and Discussion

In the Odi soils, redoximorphic features occurred at the 135 cm depth from the mineral soil surface of ODI1, 40 cm for ODI2 and 3 cm for ODI3 while Koroama soils recorded the same characteristics at the 115 cm depth from the mineral soil surface for KRM1, 40 cm for KRM2 and 12 cm for KRM3. In the NDU soils, redoximorphic characteristics were observed at 81 cm depth from the mineral soil surface of NDU1, 36 cm for NDU2 and 5 cm for NDU3 (Tables 2, 3 and 4). The three lowest layers of ODI1 soil were subject to hydromorphic influence with mottles indicating that these layers were subject to alternate wetting and drying. The colour of the first three layers of ODI2 had darker hue (10YR) but became redder (7.5YR) with depth. In the case of ODI3, redoximorphism was evident from the second to the eighth layer as common, medium distinct, reddish brown (5 YR5/3), common, medium distinct, reddish brown (5 YR 5/4), common, medium, distinct, yellowish brown (5 YR 4/6), many, medium, distinct, reddish brown (5YR 4/4), many coarse, distinct, yellowish red (5 YR 4/6), many, coarse, prominent, weak red (2.5 YR 5/2) and many, coarse, prominent, reddish brown (5 YR 5/3) mottles were present in the second, third, fourth, fifth, sixth, seventh and eighth soil layers, respectively. The alternate wetting and drying of the soils led to reduction

and subsequent release of iron oxides, accumulating in the form of strong brown, brown and red mottles on the subsurface layers of the profiles corroborating the report for Cross Rivers State floodplain soils in Nigeria by Akpan-Idiok and Ogbaji (2013). Gleying (chroma of 2 or less) was observed in the two bottom layers of the ODI2 profile which indicated longer period of submergence by water. During sampling in the dry season, the ODI2 soil profile was completely dry indicating that ground water influence occurred in the rainy season. The dark coloration of the top soil layers of ODI1 and ODI2 soils was attributed to organic matter accumulation. Darkened surface layer of ODI3 indicated humification by organic materials (Dengiz et al., 2012; Abate et al., 2014), as the soils have been fallowed for some years. In the KRM2 soils, value generally decreased with increase in depth indicating that moisture influence increased with depth. This can be explained by the fact that light reflection and purity of the spectral colour decreases when the soil was moist resulting in lower value (Dickson et al., 2021) Therefore, variation in soil colour within the profile was very obvious. Whereas dark colour in the surface was attributed to organic matter content, brown, grayish brown and gray colours were due to iron compounds at various stages of oxidation/reduction reactions as the soil was subjected to alternate wetting and drying periods.

Table 2. Morphological/Physical Characteristics of Odi Soils

Horizon	Depth cm	Soil colour	Mottles		Texture (mgkg-1)			Silt/clay ratio	Textural class	Mica flakes
			Colour	Pattern	Sand	Silt	Clay			
ODI1										
Ap	0 – 26	10 YR 3/3			310	560	130	4.3	Silt loam	Many
A	26 – 60	10 YR 4/4			410	440	150	2.9	Loam	Many
B1	60 – 78	10 YR 4/4			310	490	200	2.5	Loam	Many
B2	78 – 120	10 YR 4/4			170	670	160	4.2	Silt loam	Many

B3	120 – 135	10 YR 4/4			390	410	200	2.1	Loam	Many
C1	135 – 163	10 YR 4/4	7.5 YR 3/4	C2D	250	630	120	5.3	Silt loam	Many
C2	163 – 186	10 YR 4/4	2.5 YR 3/4	M3D	110	670	220	3	Silt loam	Many
C3	186 – 200+	10 YR 4/4	5 YR 4/4	M3P	230	650	120	5.4	Silt loam	
ODI2										
Ap	0 – 20	10 YR 3/4			410	450	140	3.2	Loam	many
A	20 – 40	10 YR 5/4			420	470	110	4.3	Loam	common
B1	40 – 110	10 YR 5/3	5 YR 6/4	F2D	310	570	120	4.8	Silt loam	common
B2	110- 141	7.5 YR 5/4	5 YR 4/4	M3D	350	510	140	3.6	Silt loam	common
B3	141 – 180	7.5YR 5/2	5 YR 3/4	M3P	210	610	180	4.4	Silt loam	common
C	180 – 200+	10 YR 5/1	5 YR 3/4	M3P	150	690	160	4.3	Silt loam	
ODI3										
Ah	0 – 3	10 YR 2/2			350	570	80	7.1	Silt loam	common
Ap1	3 – 20	10 YR 6/4	5 YR 5/3	C2D	210	630	160	3.9	Silt loam	many
Ap2	20 – 46	10 YR 6/3	5 YR 5/4	C2D	270	580	150	3.9	Silt loam	many
B1	46 – 60	10 YR 5/3	5 YR 4/6	C2D	370	530	100	5.3	Silt loam	many
B2	60 – 94	7.5 YR 4/4	5 YR 4/4	M2D	210	650	140	4.6	Silt loam	many
B3	94 – 145	10 YR 4/6	5 YR 4/6	M3D	210	650	140	4.6	Silt loam	many
C1	145 – 158	10 YR 5/4	2.5 YR 5/2	M3P	170	650	180	3.6	Silt loam	many
C2	158 – 200+	10 YR 5/4	5 YR 5/3	M3P	15.0	65.0	20.0	3.3	Silt loam	

Table 3. Morphological/Physical Characteristics of Koroama Soils

Horizon	Depth cm	Soil colour	Mottles		Texture (%)			Silt/c lay ratio	Textural class	Mica flakes
			Colour	Pattern	Sand	Silt	Clay			
KRM1										
A1	0 – 7	10 YR 3/4			240	610	150	4.1	Silt loam	many
A2	7 – 43	10 YR 4/3			200	640	140	4.6	Silt loam	many
B1	43 – 86	10 YR 3/2			210	600	190	3.2	Silt loam	many
B2	86 – 115	10 YR 3/2			160	690	150	4.6	Silt loam	many
BC	115 – 130	10 YR 4/2	7.5 YR 4/4	M2D	160	670	170	3.9	Silt loam	many
C	130 – 200+	10 YR 4/3	10 YR 4/6	M3P	200	600	190	3.2	Silt loam	
KRM2										
Ap	0 -15	10 YR 3/2			240	610	150	4.1	Silt loam	few
Ap2	15 – 23	10 YR 5/3			200	640	140	4.6	Silt loam	many
B1	23 – 40	10 YR 5/3			210	600	190	3.2	Silt loam	many
B2	40 – 64	10 YR 4/3	5 YR 4/3	C2D	160	690	150	4.6	Silt loam	many
B3	64 – 78	10 YR 5/3	5 YR 3/4	M3D	160	670	170	3.9	Silt loam	many
C1	78 – 140	10 YR 5/2	5 YR 3/4	M3P	200	600	190	3.2	Silt loam	many
C2	140 – 194+	10 YR 5/1	7.5 YR 2.5/3	M3P	180	700	120	5.8	Silt loam	
KRM3										
Ap	0 – 12	10 YR 3/2			300	610	90	6.8	Silt loam	few
Ap2	12 – 39	10 YR 5/2	5 YR 4/3	F2D	200	640	160	4	Silt loam	few
B1	39 – 59	10 YR 2/2	5 YR 3/4	M2D	100	600	300	2	Silty clay loam	few
B2	59 – 96	10 YR 5/2	7.5 YR 4/6	M3D	170	640	290	2.2	Silty clay loam	few
B3	96 – 135	10 YR 5/2	7.5 YR 4/6	M3P	160	540	300	1.8	Silty clay loam	few
C	135 – 190+	10 YR 5/2	7.5 YR 4/6	M3P	180	670	250	2.3	Silt loam	

Table 4. Morphological/Physical Characteristics of Niger Delta University Farm Soils

Horizon Design.	Depth Cm	Soil Colour Moist	Mottles		Texture (%)			Silt/clay ratio	Textural class	Mica flakes
			Clour Moist	Pattern	Sand	Silt	Clay			
NDU1										
Ap	0 – 19	10 YR 3/3			200	730	70	10.4	Silt loam	many
B1	19 – 39	10 YR 4/4			100	610	290	2.1	Silty clay loam	common
B2	39 – 71	10 YR 3/4			100	620	280	2.2	Silty clay loam	many
B3	71 – 81	10 YR 5/4			110	590	300	2	Silty clay loam	many
C1	81 – 138	10 YR 5/3	5 YR 4/4	M3D	180	720	100	7.2	Silt loam	many
C2	138 – 195+	10 YR 6/2	5 YR 4/4	M3P	210	640	150	4.3	Silt loam	
NDU2										
Ap	0 – 12	10 YR 4/4			200	610	190	3.2	Silt loam	few
Ap2	12 – 26	10 YR 4/4			220	600	180	3.3	Silt loam	few
B1	26 – 36	10 YR 5/3			130	590	280	2.1	Silty clay loam	few
B2	36 – 53	10 YR 3/4	5 YR 3/3	M3D	150	570	280	2	Silty clay loam	few
B3	53 – 116	10 YR 5/4	5 YR 5/3	M3P	190	570	240	1.9	Silt loam	many
C	116 – 190+	10 YR 6/2	7.5 YR 3/4	M3P	160	700	140	5	Silt loam	
NDU3										
A1	0-5	10 YR 3/3		M3D	160	690	150	4.6	Silt loam	common
A2	5-13	10 YR4/1	5 YR 5/3	M3P	170	690	140	4.9	Silt loam	common
AB	13-20	10 YR4/4	5 YR 5/4	M3P	160	690	150	4.6	Silt loam	many
B1	20-75	10 YR 5/4	5 YR 4/3	M3P	140	670	190	3.5	Silt loam	many
B2	75-140	10 YR5/4	5 YR 6/2	M3P	150	660	190	3.5	Silt loam	many
C	140-196+	10 YR 6/3	5 YR 6/1	M3P	150	690	160	4.3	Silt loam	

However, owing to rise and drop in water table in the profile, a lot of the fine pores at the two bottom layers were blocked, hence the two layers had chroma of 2 or less indicating longer period of submergence and that gleitization as a soil forming process has set-in in ODI2, KRM2, KRM3 and NDU2. Though the NDU3 profile colour was generally higher had chroma of 2, the chroma of the mottles of the two bottom layers was 2 or less. Medium to coarse continuous pores occurred also in the ODI3 profile and the profile was dry at the time of sampling with water table below the profile. Though the soil textural class is silt loam, clay content in the last two horizons was higher than the rest of the horizons. The occurrence of black concretions in ODI2, ODI3, and KRM1 suggested previous anthropogenic influence.

Physical Properties of the Soils

As presented in Tables 2-4, silt sized particles dominated the ODI and KRM soils followed by sand while NDU soils were also dominated by silt-sized particles but followed by clay. From the surface layer of ODI3 to the bottom, all the horizons were silt loam while ODI2 had loam as textural class in the first two layers and silt loam in the remaining layers. The silt concentration of Koroama soils (KRM1, KRM2 and KRM3) at the top and sub soil layers were far higher than 50% which may well mean that these soils have strong surface aggregation and might not be vulnerable to erosion (Dickson et al., 2021). Also, the silt concentration both in the top and subsoil layers in all the pedons was far above 50%. Using the ratings of Hazelton and Murphy

(2007), silt was rated high in the surface and subsurface layers of all the pedons. Though increased clay concentrations were noticeable in the lower layers of KRM2, KRM3, NDU2 and NDU3, no cutans were observed indicating that increased clay was not connected to clay illuviation from upper horizons to lower layers but in-situ weathering of parent materials or clay from the parent materials, suggesting that the soils were young. Essoka and Esu (2000), reported that silt/clay ratio of less than unity indicates low values and could mean that the soils are pedogenetically ferralitic in nature. Silt/clay ratios in the Odi soils ranged from 2.1 to 5.4 for ODI1, 3.2 to 4.8 for ODI2 and 3.3 to 7.1 for ODI3 and for Koroama soils, 4.1 to 4.6 with mean as 4.4 for KRM1, 1.9 to 7.4 with 5.4 as mean for KRM2 and 4 to 6 with 5.4 as mean for KRM3. The silt/clay ratios of NDU soils ranged from 2.0 to 10.4 for NDU1, 1.9 to 5.0 for NDU2 and 3.5 to 4.9 for NDU3 which were far above unity. The silt/clay ratios of the soils generally corroborated the fact that the soils were young.

Chemical Properties of the Soils

The chemical properties of the soils are presented in figures 2 to 5. pH ranged from 5.64 to 6.30 in the surface layers and 5.99 to 6.30 in the subsurface layers. Available P (mg/Kg) varied from 6 to 21 in ODI soils, 4 to 22 in KRM soils and 0.6 to 11 in NDU soils (Figure 2). The pH values of the soils fall within the moderately

acid to neutral classes according to categorization by FPDD (2012) and Jones (2003). FPDD categorization of Bayelsa State soils into pH classes indicated that soils with pH values between 5.0 – 5.5 are strongly acid, 5.6 – 6.0 as moderately acid and 6.0 – 6.5 as slightly acid, 6.6-7.2 as neutral and 7.3-7.8 as slightly alkaline. Using this categorization, the topsoil layers of NDU3 (5.42) and the subsurface layers of KRM3 (5.48) fall into strongly acid category while the remaining soils (surface layers of ODI1, ODI2, ODI3, KRM1, KRM2, KRM3, NDU1 and NDU2 as well as the subsurface layers of ODI1, ODI2, ODI3, KRM1, KRM2, NDU1, NDU2 and NDU3) were slightly acid to neutral. The optimum pH for most agricultural crops as proposed by Wong et al (2001) fall between 6.0 and 7.0 as nutrients are more available at about pH 6.5. There was noticeable increase in soil pH with increasing soil depth especially within the top 40 cm depth suggesting the likelihood of leaching loss of nutrients with the heavy rainfall experienced in the area. This agreed with the findings of Abate et al. (2014), who recorded increase in soil pH values with increase in depth and attributed to downward translocation of basic cations.

FAO (2006), and Brady and Weil (2007), gave a pH range of 5.5 to 7.0 as the preferred range for most crops because it is optimal for the overall satisfactory availability of plant nutrients.

Figure 2. pH and Available P in the Nun River Plain Soils

Khan et al (2012) on the other hand, attributed it to ferrolysis which is acidification of topsoil caused by continual displacement of bases by ferrous ion during the reduction phase associated with annual flooding. Dickson et al. (2021) report for area indicated that flooding occurs annually in this environment which comes with the long rainy season. The positive values recorded indicated that the soils were all negatively charged. Papienik et al (2007) and Alemayehu et al. (2014), attributed higher positive ΔpH values in the A-horizon to the presence of appreciable amount of negatively charged clay colloids.

Also, available P concentration decreased with increase in soil profile depth in the ODI and KRM soils which indicated the close relationship between organic matter and soil P. However, this was not the case in the NDU soils. McCauley et al. (2017), identified organic matter as the principal source of soil P for many soils. The low available P levels recorded for NDU1, NDU2 and NDU3 might be attributed to high exchangeable acidity in these soils in comparison to total exchangeable bases (Dickson et al., 2021). Abate et al. (2014), in a study of soils along a toposequence in Ethiopia reported that available P showed an increasing trend down the topographic position and a decreasing trend with depth which they attributed to an increase in clay content and a decrease in soil organic matter content. In this study, soil organic matter

content in the various horizons showed positive relationship with available P as both of them decreased with depth indicating that P decreased with decreasing concentration of organic matter.

Organic C was 0.11 to 5.26% in ODI, 0.31 to 1.84% in KRM soils and 0.93 to 2.81% in NDU soils. Total N was 0.03-0.45% in ODI soils, 0.02 to 0.11% for KRM soils and 0.02 to 0.22% in NDU soils (Figure 3). Based on the ratings given by FPDD for Bayelsa State soils, Nigeria, surface layer organic C and organic matter levels of the SMUs were medium to very high. Organic carbon (5.25%) and organic matter (9.05%) levels of the 0-3 cm layer of ODI3 (Figure 3) was rated very high which was attributed to accumulation of organic materials over time in the area. Generally, organic matter concentration in the soils of the study area decrease irregularly with increase in depth which agreed with the findings of Atofarati et al. (2012), in Nigeria and Abate et al. (2014) and Alamayehu et al. (2014) in Ethiopia. The low to moderate soil organic matter concentration, was ascribed to low biomass return to the soil, owing to the short fallow periods coupled with the bush burning cultural practice which destroy most of the organic materials. Moreover, organic matter mineralization rate is high due to high temperature and heavy rainfall as all the SMUs fall under the iso-hyperthermic temperature regime and udic moisture regime.

Figure 3. Organic C, Total N and C/N Ratio in the Nun River Plain Soils

Generally, total N distribution in the profiles decreased with increase in depth (Figure 3) revealing that organic matter is the main source of total N in the soils. The total N contents of the studied soils were directly associated with organic C contents along soil profile depths, as the highest (0.45%) value was recorded in the surface layer of ODI3 soil from Odi designated 'Ah' (Dickson et al., 2021). The total N content in all locations were higher in the surface soil layers than the underlying horizon, which is attributed to higher organic C contents in the surface. Hartz (2007), reported that soils with less than 0.07% total N have limited N mineralization potential, whereas those having total N values greater than 0.15% would be expected to mineralize sufficient amount of N during the succeeding crop cycle. Based on Hartz ratings, the surface 40cm depth of ODI3, KRM1, NDU2 and NDU3 have high mineralization potential while, ODI1, ODI2, KRM2, KRM3 and NDU1 have low mineralization potentials (Figure 3). However, using the >0.15% rating, only the surface 40cm depth of ODI3 is expected to mineralize sufficient amount of N during the succeeding crop cycle which is not good for the succeeding crops (Dickson et al, 2021). Most of the soils may therefore require N applications for successful crop production during each crop cycle.

The results of carbon to nitrogen ratio (C/N) showed irregular distribution with soil depth and topographical position in most of the soils (Figure 3). In most layers of the soils (ODI1, KRM1, KRM2, KRM3, NDU1, NDU2 and NDU3) as reported also in Dickson et al. (2021), C/N ratio especially in the plow zone was relatively higher than the common range (8:1 – 15:1) proposed by Brady and Weil (2005) for arable soils. Using the 'optimum' range (10:1 – 12:1) for arable soils (Havlin et al., 2006) only ODI2, and ODI3 soils are within the range which means oxidation and loss of organic

matter in the plow layers of the other SMUs was not very rapid which is safe for the soils considering the important role organic matter plays in the retention of soil nutrients (Dickson, 2018).

The exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K and Na) as presented in figure 4 indicated Ca^{++} dominance the exchange complex. When the mean values obtained in this study were compared with FAO (2006) ratings for Ca^{++} and Mg^{++} , the results indicated that surface 40 cm and subsurface exchangeable Ca^{++} in soils were very low while exchangeable Mg^{++} contents were low to medium. Tisdale et al. (2008) attributed low exchangeable bases in soils to acidifying properties of organic matter, high aluminium concentration and leaching loss of exchangeable bases. The low exchangeable Ca and Mg in the soils was attributed to lack of ferromagnesian minerals (Dickson, 2018), low nutrient retentive capacity, high exchangeable Al and Fe and leaching loss of the nutrients due to high rainfall. The X-ray diffraction results reported by Dickson (2018) on these soils indicated that these soils were low in ferromagnesian minerals. Biotite and vermiculite were the only ferromagnesian minerals and their concentration was low. Biotite was found in low concentrations in KRM1 only while vermiculite was detected in all the samples though in small concentrations.

Appropriate Ca/Mg ratios in soils will improve soil structure, reduce leaching loss of other nutrients, reduce weed population and generally improve the balance of most nutrients (Sharu et al., 2013). It has been reported also that, under gleization process of soil formation, exchangeable Mg^{2+} becomes the dominant cation in the exchange complex (Khan et al., 2012). It is possible the alluvial deposits from which these soils were formed were low in exchangeable Ca as the soils were considered to be in their early stages of development. The $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ ratio of less than unity indicated loss of Ca^{2+} due to gleization (Khan et al., 2012).

Figure 4. Exchangeable Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^{+} and Na^{+} in the Nun River Plain Soils

Exchangeable K in the soils (Figure 4) unlike exchangeable Ca and Mg varied from low to very high (FAO, 2006; FPDD, 2012). Most of the average values fell within medium to very high rating indicating sufficient K for crop growth. This is in confirmation of the common to many and/or abundant mica flakes observed during the field sampling. According to FAO (2006), rating for exchangeable K, soils with exchangeable K greater than 1.2 is very high, 1.2 - 0.6 high, 0.6 - 0.3 medium, 0.3 - 0.2 low and less than 0.2 very low. The K concentrations in most of the KRM and NDU soils further away from the Niger River were low to medium while ODI soils closer to the Niger River were medium to high. This development is difficult to explain since mica flakes were present in all the profiles and some ferromagnesian minerals. It is important to note that the presence of muscovite was dominant over biotite in the soils. However,

some level of variation in the distribution of basic cations down the profiles was observed which is attributed to differences in the source of the alluvial materials that formed the horizons rather than movement of nutrients from the top to the lower horizons since these soils were young and there was no marked clay illuviation.

Distribution of Clay Minerals in the Soil Mapping Units

In Table 5 and Figure 5 is the variation in the composition of clay mineral assemblage in the pedons. Ten different mineral phases were identified in the nine locations, kaolinite, quartz, muscovite ($\text{KAl}_2(\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH},\text{F})_2$) and albite ($\text{NaAlSi}_3\text{O}_8$) identified in all the locations. Quartz was the dominant mineral in the locations while kaolinite was easily detectable and dominated the

Table 4. Percentage Distribution of Clay Mineral Types in the Soil Mapping Units

Percentage Mineral in the soil										
SMU	Quartz	kaolinite	vermiculite	biotite	Muscovite	microline	albite	anorthite	chlorite	Zeolite
ODI1	65.3	2.5	0.2	Nd	3.1	19.8	9.1	Nd	Nd	Nd
ODI2	58.6	1.3	0.3	Nd	8	19	12.8	Nd	Nd	Nd
ODI3	54.5	2.5	0.2	Nd	16.4	17.9	8.5	Nd	Nd	Nd
KRM1	60.2	2.5	0.2	1.5	3.3	18.8	13.5	Nd	Nd	Nd
KRM2	46.4	1.3	0.3	Nd	14.4	11.4	24	Nd	2.2	Nd
KRM3	41.8	25.8	0.2	Nd	8.5	13.3	9.5	Nd	Nd	0.8
NDU1	46.1	18.5	0.3	Nd	7.4	12.5	14.9	Nd	Nd	0.2
NDU2	48.8	2.8	0.7	Nd	13.8	21.5	12.4	Nd	Nd	Nd
NDU3	53.7	1	0.5	Nd	10.2	18.4	16.1	Nd	Nd	nd

Note: Nd= not detected

clay fraction. Microcline, albite and muscovite of the plagioclase group were detected in all the locations. Silt-sized quartz fraction dominated the clay mineral assemblage which confirmed the recentness of the soils. Zeolite, of feldspar composition with a good deal of water in the crystal framework was present only in KRM3 and NDU1 while chlorite was present only in KRM2. There was also vermiculite, an interstratified clay mineral, present in all the SMUs (ODI1, ODI2, ODI3, KRM1, KRM2, KRM3, NDU1, NDU2 and NDU3) though not

in large quantities and biotite $[K(Mg,Fe)_2(AlSi_2O_{10})(OH,F)_2]$ only in KRM1. These findings agreed with what was recorded by Dickson et al. (2022) for the lower Niger floodplain soils in Bayelsa State. Ukubiala (2012), earlier, identified quartz, kaolinite, illite, smectite, vermiculite and interstratified types as common minerals in the silt-clay fraction of floodplain soils. Osabor et al. (2009), in the characterization of clays in Odukpani, Southeastern Nigeria reported that Kaolinite is the dominant clay mineral.

Figure 5. X-ray Diffractograms of Odi, Koroama and Niger Delta University Soils

Lekwa (1979) cited by Chude (2012), earlier reported that although kaolinite is dominant in the well-drained soils derived from coastal plain sands and sandstones, trace (5%) amounts of mica, vermiculite, and mica-vermiculite mixed layered minerals are also found in the south-south zone soils. One very important observation in this study was that as one move towards the coastal area from Odi sampling location, the concentration of kaolinite decreases while muscovite, microcline and albite became prominent. The only exceptions were KRM3 and NDU1 (Table 5) which had 25.8 and 18.5%, respectively. Chude (2012), in the literature

review on the soil fertility investigation in southern Nigeria reported how the type of clay mineral formed is related not only to the parent rock but also to the position of the soil on a toposequence and the drainage conditions. In the Obubra toposequence, kaolinite was found abundantly in the well-drained pedon on the crest of the toposequence but at the valley bottom with poor drainage, smectite became prominent. The KRM1 and NDU1 soils found on the levee crest of the toposequence of Taylor Creek and Nun River were better drained as compared to the soils located on the levee slope and lower slope on the same landscape, hence

the high concentration of kaolinite. The low concentration of ferromagnesian minerals in the clay mineralogical composition of the soils and the dominance of silt-sized quartz implied that the soils have high amount of low activity clays (LAC). Consequently, split application of recommended fertilizers rates is suggested to avert leaching loss of nutrients when applying fertilizer. In addition, cultural practices such as bush burning that destroy soil organic matter should be avoided to maintain organic matter levels in the soils. The near absence of ferromagnesian minerals may further account for the low levels of basic cations such as Mg and Ca in the soils. Consequently, Mg:K ratio in the soils was low which placed most of the pedons in the marginally suitable class for oil palm production. The presence of several K bearing minerals in the pedons such as the micas (biotite and muscovite) and the feldspars suggest that the K pool in the pedons could naturally be replenished. This agreed with the medium to high K concentration recorded in most of the pedons.

Nature of Parent Materials in Relation to Development of the Soils

Texture (Tables 2 to 4), organic carbon distribution (Figure 3) and clay mineralogy (Table 5 and Figure 5) are features commonly used as indicators of the homogeneity or otherwise of the parent materials. The distribution pattern of sand in some of the SMUs presented a lot about the parent materials. Tables 2 to 4 indicated significant change and differences in the distribution pattern of sand, silt and clay in the different horizons of the pedons. Textural diversity was observed between the different SMUs which was attributed to differences in the sources of the water-borne sediments and flow rate of the flood water at the time of deposition of the parent materials. It is obvious that finer soil particles, in suspension, probably were transported for longer period of time over greater distances and deposited at low flood period when there was less turbulence (Dickson et al., 2021). Lawal et al. (2013) reported higher amount of silt in a soil profile in Southern Guinea Savannah of Nigeria and linked it to the seasonal depositional effect

of the seasonal stream and the Suleja water reservoir inundating the area.

The organic carbon distribution pattern in the soils (Figure 3) indicated stratification as common in alluvial soils. Irregular decrease in organic matter content with depth was consistent with the properties of fluvents (Soil Survey Staff, 2014). The organic C distribution pattern in the soils indicated abrupt increase in organic C in some horizons down the profile of some SMUs which did not suggest uniform parent materials. As shown on figure 3, organic C gradually decreased from 0.95 to 0.20 to 0.11 in the 120-135cm layer, and abruptly increased to 0.26, 0.28 and 0.34% in the 135-163cm, 163-186cm and 186-200cm layers, respectively for the ODI1 soil. Apart from NDU3, all the other SMUs recorded alternate decrease and increase in organic carbon which probably indicated heterogeneity.

Conclusion

The Nun River floodplain soils of southern Nigeria are stratified with redoximorphic features and grayization, sometime reaching the A horizon. Differences in morphological, physical, chemical and mineralogical characteristics as well as heterogeneity in soil characteristics were observed, parent materials and degree of hydromorphism, moulding morphogenesis and soil formation with gleization, which is a contemporary pedogenetic process. The soils were moderately acid to slightly acid, low to moderate in available nutrients while exchange sites were dominated by Ca^{2+} . Whereas, quartz dominated the mineral phases, microcline, albite, muscovite and kaolinite were also prominent and ferromagnesian minerals concentration was low, indicating dominance of low activity clays. The study found wetness, flooding, and soil chemical and physical fertility as constraints to increased and sustainable crop production which must be taken seriously for profitable agricultural venture. Organic matter application is encouraged for sustainable crop production and if inorganic fertilizers is to be applied, split application is recommended. More detailed

mineralogical studies of the soils is recommended on a larger scale to serve as useful guide in the management of the soils for agricultural intensification and food security.

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